

the stereochemistry of the molecule should, in principle, exhibit different chemical shifts of α - and β -carbons in the isomeric pair, but no attempt appears to have been made to ascertain the validity of this concept. This prompted the investigation of ^{13}C nmr spectra of α -aryl- β -methyl-4-chloro cinnamionitriles.

Experimental

The ^{13}C nmr spectra (noise-decoupled and off-resonance) were recorded on a Varian CFT-20 NMR spectrometer operating at 20.0 MHz in the Fourier-Transform mode using approximately one molar solutions in CDCl_3 at 22° . The spectra were obtained using pulses corresponding to tilt angles between 45° and 60° with a delay of 1.3–1.6 sec. between consecutive pulses. All the chemical shifts are expressed in δ ppm. The required compounds were obtained by the reaction of *o*-carboxy benzyl cyanide with *p*-chloro acetophenone³ and the geometrical isomers were separated by column chromatography over silica gel using CHCl_3 as the eluant.

Results and Discussion

The structure of α -aryl- β -methyl cinnamionitrile possesses a unique feature which permits the delocalization of electrons in both the geometrical isomers (3-4). In the *E*-isomer the delocalization of electrons occurs between the *p*-chlorophenyl ring and the cyano group and in the *Z*-isomer between the two aromatic rings.

However, a bulky substituent placed at the *ortho* position of the α -phenyl ring makes the situation different as is evident from the Dreiding model of 1 and 2. The steric interactions make the α -*o*-carboxyphenyl ring non-coplanar to the ethylenic bond in 1 and 2. In a situation such as this the delocalization of electrons between *p*-chlorophenyl ring and the cyano group in the *E*-isomer (1) remains undisturbed but in the *Z*-isomer (2) the flow of electrons between the two aromatic rings is hindered. The effect of delocalization of electrons, as would be evident from the chemical shift of α , β and methyl carbon atoms of 1 compared to those of 2 (Table 1) indicated the deshielding of the β -carbon and shielding of the α -carbon atom in 1. A plausible explanation for this observed effect is concerned with the ease of delocalization of π -electrons which renders the α -carbon atom of 1 to resonate at higher field and β -carbon atom at lower field as compared to those for the corresponding *Z*-isomer (2). This explanation is also in agreement with the one furnished by Stradi *et al.*². The resonance of the methyl carbons in 2 at lower field may possibly be explained on the

basis of the overall geometry of the molecule in which the electron pull by the cyano group contributes towards the observed effect. Comparative study of the chemical shifts of the nitrile carbon in 1-4 indicates that the difference of the chemical shifts is independent of the influence of the delocalization of electrons.

TABLE 1 - CHEMICAL SHIFTS OF VARIOUS CARBONS OF α -ARYL- β -METHYL-4-CHLORO CINNAMONITRILES

Compound No.	Isomer	α -C	β -C	CH_3	CN	CO_2H
1	<i>E</i>	110.28	157.10	21.44	121.57	171.88
2	<i>Z</i>	111.19	155.75	24.14	121.62	171.74
3	<i>E</i>	112.09	154.63	21.58	118.73	—
4	<i>Z</i>	112.32	154.49	21.74	118.90	—

The conclusion drawn from this study reveals that the steric interactions originating because of bulky *ortho*-substituents present in the geometrical isomers 1 and 2 make the delocalization of electrons between the *p*-chlorophenyl ring and the cyano group possible only in 1. This results in the shielding of the α -carbon and deshielding of the β -carbon in the *E*-isomer (1).

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Chemical Investigation of the Leaves of *Aesculus indica*

M. K. BHATTACHARYA, P. K. GHOSH and K. S. MUKHERJEE*

Department of Chemistry, Visva-Bharati University, Santiniketan-731 235, West Bengal

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AESCULUS indica (Family-Hippocastanaceae) is a large deciduous tree with a short, straight, cylindrical bole and a spreading crown with dropping branches. It is distributed from the Indus to Nepal, generally growing in rich, moist, shady ravines on the hill tops of Kashmir, the Punjab and Uttar Pradesh at an altitude of 4000–10000 ft. It is widely used as an indigenous drug^{1,2} in various ailments. The fruits are given to horses in colic. An oil from the seeds is used externally in rheumatic complaints. In this communication we

*To whom all correspondence may be made.

report the characterization of several compounds isolated from the leaves of this plant.

Experimental

The air dried powdered leaves of *A. indica* were extracted exhaustively in turn with petroleum ether (60–80°), benzene and chloroform and finally percolated with ethanol.

The petroleum ether (60–80°) concentrate was subjected to column chromatography over Brockmann alumina. Elution of the column with petroleum ether (60–80°)-benzene (3:1) mixture yielded a solid m.p. 65–67°, identified as *n*-hentriacontane³ by comparison (m.m.p. co-tlc and superimposable ir spectra) with authentic sample

Further elution of the column with petroleum ether (60–80°)-benzene (1:1) mixture afforded colourless crystals, m.p. 84–85°. It did not give any colour reaction for triterpene or sterol and was characterised as *n*-hentriacontanol⁴ from mass spectral data, m.m.p., co-tlc and co-ir with authentic specimen.

Fraction eluted with petroleum ether (60–80°)-benzene (1:3) yielded a sterol, m.p. 135–36°, acetate, m.p. 126°, identified as β -sitosterol by direct comparison (m.m.p. and co-ir) with authentic sample. Further elution of the column with the same solvent furnished a white solid crystallised from acetone, m.p. 79–81°, oxime, m.p. 56–58°. Super imposable ir spectra, co-tlc and m.m.p. established its identity as palmitone.

The benzene, chloroform and alcoholic extracts on similar chromatographic resolution afforded only β -sitosterol.

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Studies on the Genus Piper—IX: Characterization of Abnormal Products*: Synthesis of Dihydro and Tetrahydropiperlongumic Acid

(Mrs.) NOTON BANERJEE (NEE' CHATTERJEE)** and C. P. DUTTA

Department of Chemistry, University of Kalyani, Kalyani-741 235, West Bengal

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DURING the course of our reinvestigation on the structure of the alkaloid piperlongumine (piperlongumine)^{1,2} we tried to verify the structure of the tetrahydro derivative by a synthesis which involves the condensation of 3,4,5-trimethoxycinnamoyl chloride with α -piperidone in presence of pyridine followed by simple reduction of the condensation product, dihydropiperlongumine. But the condensation reaction furnished the anhydride of 3,4,5-trimethoxy cinnamic acid⁽¹⁾ $C_{24}H_{26}O_9$ (M^+458), m.p. 185–86°, ir absorption for anhydride function (1724 and 1574 cm^{-1}) and a minor constituent, compound-A, instead of the desired product dihydropiperlongumine.

The minor constituent, compound A, $C_{17}H_{23}NO_6$ (M^+337) exhibits ir absorption bands at 3333 cm^{-1} (NH and/or OH), 1689 cm^{-1} (C=O of a nonconjugated -COOH), 1653 cm^{-1} (monosubstituted α,β -unsaturated carboxamide) and 990 cm^{-1} (*trans* -CH=CH-). PMR spectrum of the compound **I**A, studied in $CDCl_3$, shows a pair of doublets around δ 6.30 and 7.60 ($J=16$ Hz) attributed to the α - and β -protons of a styryl nucleus whereas the singlets at δ 6.73 (2H) and δ 3.90 (9H) confirm the presence of 1-substituted 3,4,5-trimethoxybenzene chromophore in the molecule. A two proton multiplet around δ 3.80 indicates the presence of a methylene group adjacent to nitrogen atom. Two other multiplets around δ 2.67 and δ 1.47 may be assigned to the remaining six methylene protons present in the molecule.

The presence of the 3,4,5-trimethoxycinnamoyl moiety is also confirmed by the formation of the base peak at m/e 221 from the molecular ion (M^+337) in the mass spectrum of the compound. The other significant fragment at m/e 19 arises by the loss of water involving -COOH group and a δ -hydrogen through a six membered transition state³.

All these spectral and chemical data can readily be explained on the basis of structure (II) for the compound A. This structure (II) is further confirmed by

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** Present Address: Rice Process Engineering Centre (Post Harvest Technology Centre), Indian Institute of Technology, Kharagpur-721 302.